

STUDY OF POSSIBILITY TO PREDETECT INITIATION SITE OF DESTRUCTION OF FLAT BRAIDED CFRP BY SQUID-NDE

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1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are composite materials with lightweight and high specific strength. They are widely used in aerospace, automotive, and sports industries [1]. Recently, braided CFRPs, in which carbon-fiber bundles are interlaced in a braided textile, have been developed and researched [2]. As the braided CFRPs have continuous carbon-fiber bundles in their longitudinal direction, complex structures with high strength can be produced [3]. Therefore, researches of the mechanical and destructive properties of the braided CFRPs are ongoing [4]. Because the strength of the braided CFRPs is determined mainly by conditions of carbon fibers, a nondestructive evaluation (NDE) method to evaluate the conditions of the carbon fibers is needed. Since the diameter of a carbon fiber of the braided CFRPs is in several μm , it is difficult to detect some breakage of the fibers by using conventional NDE methods such as x-ray testing or ultrasonic testing. On the other hand, we have focused attention on that the electric conductivity of the carbon fibers changes drastically when they are broken. A current will flow in the carbon fibers by applying voltage to the braided CFRP according to the distribution of the electric conductivity in the braided CFRP. Therefore, by measuring the current distribution in the braided CFRP with a high sensitivity and high spatial resolution, the distribution of the electric conductivity can be estimated to evaluate the conditions of the carbon fibers. We developed a NDE method in which magnetic field gradients above board specimens were measured with superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) gradiometers while

injecting ac currents in the specimens, to estimate current distributions in the specimens from the gradient distributions. So far, we applied the method to braided CFRP specimens with artificial cracks and cut-edges to demonstrate the effectiveness of the method [5, 6]. In this work, step-by-step tensile test on a braided CFRP specimen was carried out to make some breakage of the fibers, and observation and analysis of the destructive mechanism of the braided CFRPs were carried out. During the analysis, we applied the NDE method using a high-temperature superconductor (HTS) SQUID gradiometer to estimate the conditions of the carbon fibers in the specimen at certain destructive stages and discuss the effectiveness of the method.

2 Specimen and Tensile Test

2.1 Specimen

Fig. 1 (a) shows a picture of a braided CFRP specimen before tensile test. This specimen consists of 25 carbon-fiber bundles (HTS40-12k, Toho Tenax) which were braided in a flat textile with angles of $\pm 45^\circ$, and were manually fixed with epoxy resin. One bundle consists of 12000 carbon fibers whose diameter is $7 \mu\text{m}$ [7]. The width of the bundles is roughly 2 mm. Schematic image of the textile of the braided carbon-fiber bundles is shown in Fig. 1 (b). The carbon-fiber bundles are continuous from end to end in its longitudinal direction as shown in Fig. 1 (b). The length, width and thickness of the specimen are 160 mm, 41 mm and 1 mm, respectively. To inject a current into the specimen, electrodes were fixed on the left and right ends as shown in Fig. 1 (a). For the tensile test, four

aluminum tabs were attached on both faces of both ends of the specimen.

2.2 Tensile Test

In this research, tensile test was carried out to the braided CFRP specimen by using an Instron Universal Testing Machine at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. To monitor the progress of the destruction on the surface of the specimen, white watercolor was painted on it. A strain gauge was stuck on the surface of the specimen to obtain a stress-strain curve of the specimen. Figs. 2(a) and (b) show the stress-strain curve and pictures of the specimen at three stages, respectively. The strain was calculated from the displacement and original length of the specimen. The stress increased nonlinearly in the stress-strain curve from the stage (A) to the stage (B). Then, matrix crack occurred roughly along a bundle on the surface of the specimen near the left tab (indicated by a circle in Fig. 2 (b), and the stress dropped at the stage (B). With increase of the load to the specimen, the matrix crack occurred at (B) propagated toward the upper right direction, and several bundles perpendicular to the crack were broken during the propagation. Finally, we stopped the load at the stage (C) when many bundles were ruptured and the specimen was warped. In this paper, the stages (A), (B) and (C) are defined as “before loading”, “at occurrence of the first crack”, and “at occurrence of the final rupture”, respectively. The NDE method using HTS-SQUID gradiometer was applied to the specimen at the three stages.

3 NDE Using HTS-SQUID Gradiometer

3.1 Method

In order to monitor the conditions of the braided CFRP specimen under the step-by-step tensile test, the following SQUID-NDE method was applied to the specimen. By applying a voltage to a board specimen in the xy plane, a current is induced in the specimen to generate a magnetic field. The field gradients ($d B_z/dy$, $d B_z/dx$) in a xy plane close to the specimen have a relationship with the current densities (J_x , J_y) in the specimen ($d B_z/dy \cong \mu_0 J_x$, $d B_z/dx \cong -\mu_0 J_y$), according to the Maxwell's equation ($\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J}$) [8]. Accordingly, the distributions of the field gradients $d B_z/dy$ and $d B_z/dx$ in the xy plane

above the specimen are approximately analogous to the distributions of the current densities J_x and J_y . In our measurements, currents are induced in all carbon-fiber bundles equally by applying a voltage between both ends of the braided CFRP specimen, where all the bundles are naked. Then, the field gradient distributions of $d B_z/dy$ and $d B_z/dx$ above the specimen are measured using a HTS-SQUID gradiometer with a small baseline. By this method, one can obtain two-dimensional (2-D) distributions of the field gradients, which are analogous to the current densities. Breakage, density of carbon fibers, and contact resistance between carbon-fiber bundles can be estimated from the distributions.

So far, it has shown that equal currents flow in all bundles in a normal uniformly braided CFRP specimen in our previous studies [5,6]. Fig. 3 shows the schematic image of the induced currents in the specimen, the generated magnetic fields and the field gradient. As shown in the figure, as bundles with angles of $\pm 45^\circ$ overlap at any point of the specimen, the resultant sum of the currents at the point has only the x -component. This current generates a magnetic field with two peaks at both sides of the current with the opposite poles. In the figure, a schematic image of the z -component of the magnetic field, which is measured by the SQUID gradiometer, is shown. As such the current and the magnetic field are induced in and generated above the entire braided CFRP specimen, the magnetic fields vanish each other in the center of the specimen, and the magnetic fields remain above the edges of the specimen. Concerning the $d B_z/dy$ distribution, peaks with the same pole are distributed above the both edges, and the $d B_z/dy$ distribution in the center of the specimen is lower and uniform than those above the edges. The peaks above the edges are due to so-called “edge effect”, which appears in a case that a uniform current flows in a board specimen such as metals. As to the braided CFRP, the same effect occurred in a case that equivalent currents flowed in all the bundles [5,6].

3.2 System

A schematic diagram of a measurement system with a HTS-SQUID gradiometer used in this work is shown in Fig. 4. The details of the system are described in the references [9-11]. A HTS-SQUID gradiometer outputs the voltages that are

proportional to the magnetic gradients ($d B_z/dy$, $d B_z/dx$) in a case of a board specimen in the xy plane. In this system, a planer HTS-SQUID gradiometer with two square coils ($1 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$), which forms a differential pick-up coil, was employed. By applying an ac voltage between the ends of the specimen, an ac current was induced, and the field gradient ($d B_z/dy$, $d B_z/dx$) distributions above the specimen were measured by the SQUID gradiometer through a lock-in amplifier.

3.3 Measurements

In the experiments, the tensile test to the specimen was stopped when some cracks occurred. And then, the field gradients above the specimen off the load machine were measured while inducing an ac current of 7 mA at 800 Hz in the specimen at the three stages shown in Fig. 2 (b). The scanning interval and the scanned range were 1 mm in the x and y directions and $70 \text{ mm} \times 41 \text{ mm}$, respectively. The standoff distance between the gradiometer and the surface of the specimen was 2 mm in a case of the specimen before loading and was 3 mm in the other cases.

4 Experimental Results

Figs. 5(a), (b) and (c) show the $d B_z/dy$ distributions above the specimen before loading, at occurrence of the first crack, and at occurrence of the final rupture. In all the measurements, the currents flow from the left to the right in the figures, and black in the figures shows that the field gradient $d B_z/dy$ is higher at the position. As mentioned before, the gradient $d B_z/dy$ in the xy plane close to the surface of the specimen is proportional to the x -component current J_x in the specimen. The display ranges are same in the three figures.

As shown in Fig. 5 (a), there are peaks of the gradient above the both edges due to the edge effect. There are no large changes in the center of the specimen compared to the both edges. Stripes along the bundles aligning with the angles of $\pm 45^\circ$ can be seen in the almost whole distribution. As shown in chapter 3.1, in the virgin specimen, the equivalent currents must flow in all the bundles, and at each position, two bundles overlap. As a result, since the y -component currents J_y vanish each other, the current distribution is analogous to a distribution

where only the x -component currents flow uniformly. On the other hand, the stripes along the bundles aligning with the angles of $\pm 45^\circ$ appeared probably due to such as the non-uniform density, imperfect overlapping and directions of the bundles. We took particular note of a line A with an angle of $+45^\circ$, where the field gradient is lower. With an assumption that the equivalent currents flowed in the carbon-fiber bundles of the specimen, a line along a bundle where the field gradient is lower compared to the other points should mean that the density of the bundle is lower because either the width of the bundle should be a bit wider or the overlapping of another bundle on the bundle is somehow imperfect.

Fig. 5 (b) shows the result of the specimen at occurrence of the first crack. The spatial resolution and signal intensity are lower than those in Fig. 5 (a) because the standoff distance was 1 mm longer. Therefore, the stripes in the center of the specimen are blurred in the figure. Despite the occurrence of the first crack in the stage (B) (see Fig. 2 (b)), the distribution in Fig. 5 (b) was roughly same as that in Fig. 5 (a). If some bundles were broken at the occurrence of the first crack, the current and field gradient distributions would change. Therefore, the roughly same distributions between them mean that there occurred only the matrix crack in the stage (B). However, we note that the matrix crack occurred approximately near the line A, where the field gradients were lower in both Figs. 5(a) and (b). After the measurement of Fig. 5 (b), additional tensile test caused propagation of the matrix crack, and the breakage of the bundles occurred on the line A. Fig. 5 (c) shows the result of the specimen at occurrence of the final rupture. The field gradient $d B_z/dy$ is very low in the lower area of the line A in Fig. 5 (c). The distribution indicates that current did not flow in the bundle in the area. On the other hand, in the upper area of the line A, the gradient $d B_z/dy$ increased significantly compared to Figs. 5(a) and (b), and there is a peak in the distribution around the upper end of the line A. The result suggests that the most current flowed through the upper area of the specimen. From these results, it is suggested that the carbon-fiber bundles with the angle of -45° were broken on the line A, and the current flowed through the continuous bundles in the upper middle area of the specimen.

It is noteworthy that the breakage of the bundles occurred on the line A where the field gradient was lower in even the virgin specimen.

5. Observation of Cross-section of Braided CFRP

To investigate the conditions of the carbon-fiber bundles on the line A, where the field gradient density is low, the specimen was cut, and then the cross-section of the specimen was observed after the tensile test. As the breakage was serious near the line A, we cut the specimen on the lines shown in the inset of Fig. 6, and then we observed the cross-section using a microscope. Fig. 6 shows the microscopic photograph of the cross-section of the specimen and the profile of the B_z/dy distribution above the line, which was derived from the result on the virgin specimen. The gradients $d B_z/dy$ are higher at I and IV, where corresponds to the both edges of the specimen. This is because not only the density of the carbon-fiber bundles is higher at the edges, where the bundles are returning as shown in the photo of Fig. 6, but also because of the above-mentioned edge effect. On the other hand, the gradient dB_z/dy at II and III are a bit lower amongst the middle of the specimen. These points correspond to the circled area, where the density of the bundles is lower as shown in the photo. The results in Fig. 6 indicate that the field gradient distributions measured by the SQUID-NDE system have a relationship with the density of the carbon-fiber bundles. From these results, it is estimated that the density of the bundles on the line A in Fig. 5 (a) must be lower. In a case that there is an area or a line with lower bundle density in a braided CFRP specimen, a matrix crack may occur on the place where the density of matrix is higher when a tensile loading is applied to the specimen. As a result, propagation of the matrix crack and breakage of the bundles will occur due to stress concentration on the place. Finally, it is indicated that the density of the carbon-fiber bundles should have a relationship with the strength of braided CFRPs, and that there is a possibility to predict the initiation site of destruction in braided CFRPs by using the SQUID-NDE method, which can detect low bundle density area with its high sensitivity and spatial resolution.

6. Summary

We applied the current-injection-based NDE method using the HTS-SQUID gradiometer for the braided CFRP before, during and after the tensile test. In the measurement results, the line oriented toward the angle of $+45^\circ$ with the lower field gradient was detected above the virgin specimen. By the observation of the cross-section of the specimen, it is verified that the intensity of the field gradient corresponds to the density of the carbon-fiber bundles. From these results, we showed that the density of the carbon-fiber bundles can be estimated, and there is a possibility to predict the initiation site of the destruction in braided CFRPs by the SQUID-NDE method.

Fig. 1. Braided CFRP specimen
 (a) Picture of specimen with aluminum tabs.
 (b) Schematic image of braided carbon-fiber bundles.

Fig.2.(a)Pseudostress-straincurve.
(b)BraidedCFRPspecimenatthreestages.

Fig.3.Schematicimageofcurrentflowingin braidedcarbon-fiberbundlesandgenerated magneticfield B_z andfieldgradient dB_z/dy .

Fig.5.Distributionsof $d B_z/dy$ above specimen. (a)Beforeloading.(b)Atoccurrenceofthe firstcrack.(C)Atoccurrenceofthefinalrupture

Fig.6. Cross-section of cut specimen and profile of field gradient above the cutline.

References

- [1] G. Messina and S. Santangelo "Carbon: The Future Material For Advanced Technology Applications (topics In Applied Physics)" . 1st edition, Springer-Verlag, 2006.
- [2] P. J. Falzon, and I. Herszberg "Mechanical performance of 2-D braided carbon/epoxy composites". *Composites Science and Technology* , Vol.58, No.2, pp253-265, 1998.
- [3] P. Potluri, A. Manan, M. Francke, R. Day "Flexural and torsional behavior of biaxial and triaxial braided composite structures". *Composite Structures* , Vol. 75, pp377-386, 2006.
- [4] R. Inai, E. C. Chirwa, H. Saito, T. Uozumi, A. Nakai and H. Hamada "Experimental Investigation on the Crushing Properties of Carbon Fiber Braided Composite Tubes". *International Journal of Crashworthiness*, Vol.5, No.8, pp513-521, 2003.
- [5] Y. Shinyama, Y. Hatsukade, S. Tanaka, Y. Takai, M. S. Aly-Hassan, A. Nakai and H. Hamada "Nondestructive Evaluation of Braided Carbon Fiber Composites Using High Tc SQUID". *Advanced Materials Research* , Vols. 123-125, pp 835-838, 2010.
- [6] Y. Shinyama, Y. Hatsukade, S. Tanaka, Y. Takai, M. S. Aly-Hassan, A. Nakai and H. Hamada "Nondestructive Evaluation of Braided Carbon Fiber Composites with artificial defect Using HTS-SQUID gradiometer". *Physica C* , in press, 2011.
- [7] <http://www.tohotenax.com/tenax/jp/products/>
- [8] Y. Hatsukade, M.S. Aly-Hassan, N. Kasai, H. Takashima, H. Hatta and A. Ishiyama "SQUID-NDE method on damaged area and damage degree of defects in composite materials". *IEEE Trans. Appl. Supercond.* , Vol13, pp207-210, 2003.
- [9] Y. Hatsukade, T. Inaba, Y. Maruno and S. Tanaka "Mobile cryocooler-based SQUID NDE system utilizing active magnetic shielding". *IEEE Trans. Appl. Supercond.* , Vol.15, No.2, pp723-728, 2005.
- [10] Y. Hatsukade, T. Takahashi, T. Yasui, M. Tsubaki, M. Fukumono and S. Tanaka "Study on nondestructive inspection using HTS-SQUID for friction stir welding between dissimilar metals". *Physica C* , Vols.463-465, pp1038-1042, 2007.
- [11] A. Miyazaki, Y. Hatsukade, H. Matsuura, T. Maeda, A. Suzuki and S. Tanaka "Detection of wire element breakage in power transmission line using HTS-SQUID". *Physica C* , Vol.469, Nos.15-20, pp1643-1648, 2009.